

Improving SMEs Performance Through Competitive Advantage with Entrepreneurial Marketing (SMEs in Bandung City)

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Abstract

SMEs play an essential and strategic role in the regional economy. Additionally, to aid COVID-19 efforts and promote these small enterprises. However, the situation is quite profitable for SME hand sanitizer producers because of the many comparable businesses that have sprung up. The purpose of this study was to investigate the contribution of entrepreneurial marketing to competitive advantage and its effect on business factors such as the performance of SMEs. Using a questionnaire as a data collecting instrument, this study employs a survey as its approach. SMEs hand sanitizers populate the city of Bandung, and path analysis is used to analyze the data. This study reveals that entrepreneurial marketing influences competitive advantage and company performance, and that competitive advantage also influences business performance.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial Marketing, Competitive Advantage, Business Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of the new coronavirus or Corona Virus Disease 2019 covid-19, which became horrifying in everyday life and the domestic economy, especially in terms of consumption, companies, economic zones, and small businesspeople, ushered in the year 2020. Several businesses failed during the coronavirus pandemic (Sadalia et al., 2020). There are representatives from the transportation, manufacturing, tourism, and food and beverage industries. Businesses dealing with medications gain substantially from a pandemic, such as pharmaceuticals and sanitary items. The Covid-19 virus outbreak, which has been raging for the past two years, has made people more aware of the necessity of leading a healthy lifestyle. To avoid virus infection, carrying hand sanitizer outside the house has become a new way of life.

According to the findings of a recent Nielsen poll, four product categories have shown considerable growth year over year. Hand sanitizer products climbed by over 200 percent, as did liquid hand soap by 285 percent. Then there is liquid antiseptic, which increased by 233 percent, and wet tissue sales, which increased by 151 percent. The growth in sales of these products is attributable to the fact that health and cleanliness have become extremely important during the Covid-19 pandemic. Consumer behavior is also altered. Forty-four percent of consumers said they eat Health Products more frequently, while 37 percent said they use Vitamin Drinks more frequently. According to Hellen Katherina, Executive Director of Media Nielsen (Indonesia), health issues have been a public concern since the number of Covid-19 cases has increased.

It is no surprise that the health-support product sector is booming. Furthermore, according to data from the Ministry of Health, from the start of the COVID-19 case in February 2020 until today, the number of makers of medical products such as masks, hand sanitizers, and thermometers has increased significantly.

According to the research of Faddila, S. P., Nurlenawati, N., and Fadli, U. M. D. (2021), Hamid, E., and Susilo, Y. (2011), SMEs play an essential and strategic role in the regional economy. Additionally, to aid Covid-19 efforts and promote these small enterprises. The WHO has issued standards for producing readily available hand sanitizers. However, because of the many comparable businesses that have sprung up, the current situation is quite profitable for SME hand sanitizer producers. However, circumstances must still be followed by competitive advantage so that it separates itself from competing products. This is also assisted by entrepreneurial marketing, which can grab market opportunities so that marketing can continue to operate, resulting in better business performance (Trocikowski, 2007; Glabiszewski, 2010). With the preceding in mind, the goal of this study is to find a reason for company success in terms of entrepreneurial marketing and competitive advantage in Bandung's SMEs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurial Marketing

Marketing and entrepreneurship are often thought to be two distinct academic disciplines. Entrepreneurial marketing is now a distinct discipline that a business owner can use as a top small business solution (Tkachenko et al., 2018; Gagnidze, 2019; Nikolov, 2019). Marketing and entrepreneurship disciplines, as well as organizations looking for a competitive edge, have acknowledged and endorsed entrepreneurial marketing (Schulte & Eggers, 2010). In contrast to the traditional marketing mindset, an entrepreneur may deploy marketing efforts in a variety of ways.

Entrepreneurial marketing, according to Morrish et al. (2010), is the process of reviewing the environment on a regular basis to uncover or create new opportunities, and then effectively exploiting those opportunities to sustain a competitive advantage. Entrepreneurial Marketing businesses are proactive and imaginative in taking the lead or obtaining clients rather than reactive to client needs (Schindehutte, Morris, and Kocak, 2008; Byczkowska & Majzel, 2020).

Competitive Advantage

The company's capacity to win the competition will be determined by how it responds to changes (Mirkovic & Milovanovic, 2015; Maslak et al., 2016; Nikolic et al., 2019; Wisniewska, 2010). The company's response to changes in worldwide competition patterns typically takes the following forms: a. Changes in business size b. Product modifications c. Establishing new collaborations with other organizations (in A. Nainggolan, 2018). According to Day and Wensley (in Rangkuti, 2003), competitive advantage must be regarded as a dynamic process that occurs because of change rather than as a single outcome. Sources of advantage, positioning advantage, and performance outcomes are all part of the competitive advantage process.

Competitive advantage, according to David (2006), is everything that a company does better than its competitors. When one company can do something that another cannot or when one company has something that the other has not. Competitive advantage is a company's capacity to design, manufacture, and superior market products to competitors, taking price and quality into account (D'Cruz, 1992 in Samoedra, Suryana, et al. 2019; Maslak et al., 2017).

Business Performance

Organizational goals are the measure of corporate performance, according to Hult et al. (2003). Employee and management perceptions of the company's performance are used to calculate subjective measures of success. Sales volume, profitability, and market share are operational metrics of corporate performance (Najib & Kiminami, 2011). The concept of micro firm performance has been investigated in a number of research. Nonetheless, it lacks a precise definition of firm performance, which relates to the manner in which an organization generates value to its stakeholders. In other terms, it demonstrates how well SMEs' management utilize their resources. It is a measurement of an organization's efforts to achieve its goals and objectives. When microbusinesses conduct operations that satisfy their owners, customers, and other stakeholders, they achieve their objectives. Purcarea et al., 2013; Al-Ansari et al., 2013; Aminu & Shariff, 2014; Al-Ansari et al., 2013). Because of the critical role that SMEs play in economic and technical progress, there has been a lot of attention in the literature. On the other side, several studies have indicated that organizations develop a better and novel technique, service, or product for the market and that the consequences of innovation have a favorable impact on the rate of commercialization and innovation creation (Al-Ansari et al., 2013; Sikora et al., 2017; Burkhanov, 2010). Measuring company success is a critical issue for academics and managers in today's economy. "The operational ability to satisfy the desires of the company's significant shareholders" is a standard definition of business performance (Smith & Reece, 1999).

According to Radipere&Dhliwayo (2014), business performance is the extent to which a company fulfills its objectives. Additionally, firm performance can be described as a corporation's capacity to satisfy organizational and key stakeholder objectives. Small and medium-sized businesses that perform well in their operations are more likely to be sustainable and to be able to take advantage of global market possibilities (I. M. Aminu, M. N. M. Shariff, 2015).

Research Paradigm

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Hypothesis

- H1: Competitive Advantage is influenced by entrepreneurial marketing.
- H2: SME performance is significantly influenced by competitive advantage.
- H3: SME performance is significantly influenced by entrepreneurial marketing.
- H4: SME performance is influenced by entrepreneurial marketing through competitive advantage.

METHOD

The participants in this study are from SME Hand Sanitizer in Bandung. Five SMEs in Diskopumkm Bandung City make up the population. Questionnaires, interviews, observation, and literature research were utilized to gather data for this paper. Path analysis is the data analysis technique used in this study.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Path Analysis

Multiple linear regression is an extension of path analysis, or multiple linear regression is an extension of path analysis. For the purpose of determining how power relations between variables (the causal model) stated before the theory affect the results of multiple linear regression, path analysis is used. In order to assess the effect of independent factors on the needed variables, multiple linear regression was used. The following are the outcomes of a multiple regression analysis conducted with SPSS version 20.0:

Path Coefficient Model I

The following are the regression findings between Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) factors and Competitive Advantage (Y), as determined using the SPSS version 20.0 program (Ghozali, 2018):

**Table 1. Regression Analysis Model I
Coefficients**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.467	3.128		2.707	.042
	X	.880	.733	.473	2.200	.024

a. Dependent Variable: Y
Source: Data Processing SPSS 20.0

As seen in the "Coefficient" table from Regression Model I, the independent variable, Entrepreneurial Marketing (X), has a significance value of 0.024, which is less than 0.05. Study findings demonstrate a substantial influence of Regression Model I's Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) on Competitive Advantage (Y).

Coefficient of Determination Model I

To determine how well an independent variable can explain a dependent variable, we use the coefficient of determination. Almost all the information needed to forecast the dependent variable's variation is provided by the independent variable when the Adjusted R Square value is close to one. For Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) and Competitive Advantage (Y), the coefficient of determination is as follows:

Table 2. Coefficient of Determination Model 1

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.573 ^a	.328	.318	.39078

a. Predictors: (Constant), X
Source: Data Processing SPSS 20.0

In the "Model Summary" table, the R Square value is 0.328. An analysis of this data shows that entrepreneurial marketing (X) has a 32.8 percent impact on competitive advantage (Y), with the rest coming from other factors that were not included in this study. The formula $e1 = (1-0.328) = 0.820$ may be used to compute the value of e1. Structural model I's flow chart looks like this:

Figure 2. Path Analysis Model I

Path Coefficient Model II

Based on the results of the analysis using the SPSS version 20.0 Ghozali, 2018 program, the regression results between Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) variables and Competitive Advantage (Y) are as follows:

Table 3. Regression Analysis Model II

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.670	3.501		3.334	.020
	X	.618	.593	.615	4.727	.023
	Y	.399	.319	.420	4.253	.028

a. Dependent Variable: Z
Source: Data Processing SPSS 20.0

Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) = 0.023 and Competitive Advantage (Y) = 0.028, according to the results of Regression Model II in the "Coefficient" table, are less than 0.05 significant variables. In this study, the Regression Model II variables Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) and Competitive Advantage (Y) have a significant influence on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (Z).

Coefficient of Determination Model II

The coefficient of determination measures the capacity of the independent variable to explain the dependent variable. When the Adjusted R Square value is close to one, the independent variable gives nearly all the information necessary to predict the variation in the dependent variable. The following are the results of the coefficient of determination between the variables of Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) and Competitive Advantage (Y):

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination Model II
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.806 ^a	.650	.476	.27857

a. Predictors: (Constant), Y, X
Source: Data Processing SPSS 20.0

In the "Model Summary" table, the R Square value is 0.650. This reveals that entrepreneurial marketing (X) and competitive advantage (Y) contribute 65 percent to SME performance (Z), with the remaining 35 percent coming from other variables not studied in this study. The formula $e1 = (1-0.650) = 0.592$ can be used to find the value of e2. As a result, the path diagram of structural model II is as follows:

Figure 3. Path Analysis Model II

Hypothesis Test

1. Analysis of the Effect of *Entrepreneurial Marketing (X)* on *Competitive Advantage (Y)*. The significant value of Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) was 0.0240.05 based on the analysis results. As a result, it can be inferred that Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) has a direct and significant impact on Competitive Advantage (Y).
2. Analysis of the Effect of Competitive Advantage (Y) on SME Performance (Z).
3. A significant value of 0.028 0.05 Y was obtained from the analysis results. As a result, it can be argued that Competitive Advantage (Y) directly impacts SME performance (Z).
4. Analysis of the Effect of Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) on SME Performance (Z). The significant value of Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) was 0.0230.05 based on the analysis results. As a result, it can be argued that Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) has a direct and significant impact on SME performance (Z).
5. Analysis of the Effect of Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) Through Competitive Advantage (Y) on SME Performance (Z). The direct effect of Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) on Y is 0.615. The indirect effect of Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) through Competitive Advantage (Y) on SME Performance (Z) is the multiplication of the beta values of X against Y and the beta values of Y against Z, which is $0.473 \times 0.420 = 0.199$. The total effect of Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) on SME Performance (Z), which includes both the direct and indirect effects, is $0.615 + 0.199 = 0.814$. According to the calculation results, the direct influence value is 0.615, and the indirect effect is 0.199. This suggests that entrepreneurial marketing (X) has a significant impact on SME performance via competitive advantage (Y) (Z).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that: 1) Because a significance value of $0.024 > 0.05$ H_0 is accepted and H_0 is rejected, Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) has a substantial effect on Competitive Advantage (Y). That is to say; the first hypothesis is plausible in the sense that each SME must be aware of market conditions to successfully advertise their products and get a competitive advantage over other SMEs. The bigger the Jatim Park Group's Entrepreneurial Marketing, the greater the Competitive Advantage; 2) Because a significance value of $0.024 > 0.05$ H_0 is accepted and H_0 is rejected, Competitive Advantage (Y) has a substantial effect on SME Performance (Z); 3) Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) has a significant effect on SMEs' performance since a significance value of $0.023 > 0.05$ H_0 is accepted, and H_0 is refused (Z). This is because small business performance is constantly influenced by entrepreneurial marketing. If small firms want to survive, they must focus on targeted entrepreneurial marketing; and 4) Entrepreneurial Marketing (X) influences SME success through competitive advantage (Y) (Z). SMEs are crucial in marketing and developing their products, determining which product marketing strategies are appropriate, being proactive in seeking out new business opportunities, and having the courage to take risks in developing effective and efficient new business models to gain a competitive advantage. SMEs can exploit this competitive advantage to grow their businesses and reach a larger market.

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